

Syllabus Introduction to in silico medicine

1. Introduction

The learning goals indicate the requirements of each lecture of the course 'Introduction to in silico medicine' (6 ECTS). Based on these requirements the instructors can format their lecture based on their own teaching preferences, knowledge and experience, while ensuring a qualitative introductory course on in silico medicine. Note that some learning goals are formulated for more than one lecture. This does not mean that the learning goals should be achieved in each of these lectures. It is the aim that the learning goals are achieved in at least one of the lectures, but how they are distributed over the lectures is up to the preferences of the instructor.

2. Overview lectures and exercise sessions

Week	Lecture (2h)	Topic lecture	Exercise session (4h)	Topic exercise session
1	L01	Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?	P01	Relevant software tools - Part I
2	L02	From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare?	P02	Relevant software tools - Part II
3	L03	In silico medicine: ethical and legal considerations	P03	From clinical problem to digital twin
4	L04	Regulatory and standardisation aspects	P04	Ethical, legal, regulatory and standardisation guidelines
5	L05	Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro experimentation	P05	Development of an in silico model as replacement of in vitro experimentation
6	L06	Examples of in silico medicine: reduction of animal experimentation	P06	Development of an in silico model as replacement of animal experimentation
7	L07	Examples of in silico medicine: refinement of human experimentation	P07	Development of an in silico model as refinement of human experimentation
8	L08	In silico trials for medical devices	P08	Development of an in silico trial for a medical device - Part I
9	L09	In silico trials for medicinal products	P09	Development of an in silico trial for a medical device - Part II
10	L10	Communication in interdisciplinary settings	P10	Development of an in silico trial for a medicinal product - Part I
11	L11	Clinical applications of in silico medicine	P11	Development of an in silico trial for a medicinal product - Part II
12	L12	Industrial applications of in silico medicine	P12	Communication on in silico medicine

3. Lectures

L01: Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Understand the complexity of dealing with predictions about human health;*
- *Identify the origins of barriers against adoption of in silico technologies (complexity, redundancy, stochasticity, culture);*
- *Summarize first examples of digital twins and in silico trials developed;*
- *Assess the value of the in silico trials in the development of new medical products;*
- *Outline the 3R concept that led in silico trials;*
- *Illustrate how in silico technologies might be of help to ensure and extend the healthcare, given how the world population is growing;*
- *Explain what the virtual human twin will be.*

L02: From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare?

Applicable ILOs

H2.1: Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico medicine

Learning goals

- *Formulate a definition of a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Summarize the potential benefits of using a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Clarify the main challenges to integrate in silico medicine in the current clinical practice;*
- *Identify the subsequent steps of the workflow that translates a clinical problem to a digital twin;*
- *Give two examples of existing clinical problems that could benefit from in silico medicine.*

L03: In silico medicine: ethical and legal considerations

Applicable ILOs

H3.1: Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles

Learning goals

- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from an ethical perspective;*

- *Elucidate the state-of-the-art legal framework for in silico medicine and identify potential voids;*
- *Explain the importance of a legal framework in in silico medicine based on an example case.*

L04: Regulatory and standardisation aspects

Applicable ILOs

H3.4.1: Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards

H3.4.2: Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies

Learning goals

- *Showcase the importance of a regulatory and standardisation framework in in silico medicine with an example;*
- *Elucidate the state-of-the-art of the regulatory and standardisation frameworks in the United States and EU;*
- *Identify the regulatory pathways that should be followed for a given application of in silico medicine;*
- *Critically evaluate the state-of-the-art regulatory and standardisation frameworks.*

L05: Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro experimentation

Applicable ILOs

H4.1: Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

Learning goals

- *Give three examples of in silico medicine that have been used to, at least partially, replace in vitro experimentation;*
- *Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of replacing in vitro experiments by in silico medicine;*
- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace in vitro experimentation for a given case study.*

L06: Examples of in silico medicine: reduction of animal experimentation

Applicable ILOs

H4.1: Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

Learning goals

- Give three examples of *in silico* medicine that have been used to reduce the number of animal experiments;
- Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of replacing animal experiments by *in silico* medicine;
- Identify how *in silico* medicine can be applied to reduce animal experimentation for a given case study.

L07: Examples of *in silico* medicine: refinement of human experimentation

Applicable ILOs

H4.1: Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of *in vitro*, animal, or human experimentation

Learning goals

- Give three examples of *in silico* medicine that have been used to refine human experimentation;
- Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of refining human experiments by *in silico* medicine;
- Identify how *in silico* medicine can be applied to refine human experimentation for a given case study.

L08: *In silico* trials for medical devices

Applicable ILOs

H4.14: Use *in silico* methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy and evaluate the cost-effectiveness of candidate diagnostics or new interventions

Learning goals

- Formulate a definition of medical devices in the context of *in silico* medicine;
- Outline a typical workflow for the development of *in silico* trials for medical devices;
- Give two examples of *in silico* trials for medical devices;
- Critically reflect on a given case study of an *in silico* trial for medical devices in relation to the regulatory and ethical consideration;
- Showcase how *in silico* methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medical devices.

L09: *In silico* trials for medicinal products

Applicable ILOs

H4.14: Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy and evaluate the cost-effectiveness of candidate diagnostics or new interventions

Learning goals

- *Formulate a definition of medicinal products in the context of in silico medicine;*
- *Distinguish between in silico trial for medical devices and medicinal products;*
- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medicinal products;*
- *Give two examples of in silico trials for medicinal products;*
- *Critically reflect on a given case study of an in silico trial for medicinal products in relation to the regulatory and ethical consideration;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medicinal products.*

L10: Communication in interdisciplinary settings

Applicable ILOs

H2.2: Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication

H2.3: Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication

H2.11: Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to biomedical researchers

Learning goals

- *Explain technical terms such as segmentation, registration, meshing and in silico modeling in layman's terms;*
- *Explain credibility terms such as verification, validation and uncertainty quantification in layman's terms;*
- *Identify how in silico models can contribute to a given clinical need;*
- *Formulate technical requirements for an in silico model based on communication with healthcare professionals;*
- *Formulate credibility and safety requirements for an in silico model based on communication with healthcare professionals.*

L11: Clinical applications of in silico medicine

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Summarize three state-of-the-art applications of in silico medicine used in clinical practice;*
- *Evaluate the added value of a given clinical application of in silico medicine to the clinical practice;*
- *Identify which aspects of a given clinical application of in silico medicine require optimization to improve the clinical application.*

L12: Industrial applications of in silico medicine

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Summarize three state-of-the-art applications of in silico medicine used in industry;*
- *Evaluate the added value of a given application of in silico medicine to the company and its customers;*
- *Outline how a company could utilize in silico medicine to develop and/or optimize commercial products.*

4. Exercise sessions

The learning goals indicated in grey correspond to learning goals that have also been formulated for the lectures. By pursuing the same learning goal in a different context (e.g. understanding an example during the lecture and applying a concept during the exercise session), a better understanding of the considered aspect is expected.

P01: Relevant software tools - Part I

Description

Student follow tutorials of the different types of software that they will need in the development of in silico model.

For example: segmentation software, meshing software, finite element software, computational fluid dynamics software, ABM software, etc.

Learning goals

- *Reproduce the steps presented by a tutorial in order to develop a prescribed model in the in silico software;*
- *Formulate which algorithms are used by the applied software to calculate the result;*
- *Explain the meaning and functionality of each step needed to develop the in silico model;*
- *Summarize the subsequent steps needed to develop the in silico model.*

P02: Relevant software tools - Part II

Description

Student follow tutorials of the different types of software that they will need in the development of in silico model.

For example: segmentation software, meshing software, finite element software, computational fluid dynamics software, ABM software, etc.

It is recommended that a different type of software is considered compared to PO1, to allow the students to get acquainted to a variety of in silico software tools.

Learning goals

- *Reproduce the steps presented by a tutorial in order to develop a prescribed model in the in silico software;*
- *Formulate which algorithms are used by the applied software to calculate the result;*
- *Explain the meaning and functionality of each step needed to develop the in silico model;*
- *Summarize the subsequent steps needed to develop the in silico model.*

P03: From clinical problem to digital twin

Description

The students develop a workflow to translate a given clinical problem into a digital twin. The students critically discuss the benefits and challenges related to the use of the suggested digital twin in the clinical practice.

Learning goals

- *Summarize the potential benefits of using a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Clarify the main challenges to integrate in silico medicine in the current clinical practice;*
- *Identify the subsequent steps of the workflow that translates a clinical problem to a digital twin;*

P04: Ethical, legal, regulatory and standardisation guidelines

Description

The students look up and determine the applicable regulatory pathways and standardisation guidelines for given example cases of in silico medicine. They think about how they can handle each of the required steps in the workflow. The students look up and summarize the ethical and legal aspects that are relevant for the given example cases and discuss them in relation to the use of the in silico model under subject.

Learning goals

- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from an ethical perspective;*
- *Identify the regulatory pathways that should be followed for a given application of in silico medicine;*
- *Critically evaluate the state-of-the-art regulatory and standardisation frameworks.*

P05: Development of an in silico model as replacement of in vitro experimentation

Description

The students develop an in silico model aimed at replacing a given in vitro experiment. The students determine the relevant geometry, boundary conditions and loading conditions and use proper software tools to develop the model.

Learning goals

- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace in vitro experimentation for a given case study;*
- *Implement an in silico model to serve as replacement of a given in vitro experiment with state-of-the-art software tools;*

- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model that serves as replacement of a given in vitro experiment;*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model that serves as replacement of a given in vitro experiment.*

P06: Development of an in silico model as replacement of animal experimentation

Description

The students develop an in silico model aimed at replacing a given animal experiment. Based on a given geometry, the students determine the relevant boundary and loading conditions and use proper software tools to develop the model.

Learning goals

- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace in animal experimentation for a given case study;*
- *Implement an in silico model to serve as replacement of a given animal experiment with state-of-the-art software tools;*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model that serves as replacement of a given animal experiment;*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model that serves as replacement of a given animal experiment.*

P07: Development of an in silico model as refinement of human experimentation

Description

The students develop an in silico model aimed at refining a given human experiment. Based on a given geometry, the students determine the relevant boundary and loading conditions and use proper software tools to develop the model.

Learning goals

- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to refine human experimentation for a given case study.*
- *Implement an in silico model to contribute to the refinement of a given human experiment with state-of-the-art software tools.*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model that contributes in the refinement of a given human experiment.*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model that contributes in the refinement of a given human experiment.*

P08: Development of an in silico trial for a medical device - Part I

Description

The students develop an in silico trial for a given case study on a medical device with defined specifications. In the development process, the students situate the in silico trial in the development process of the medical device, determine the aim of the in silico trial, the available input and the desired output and create the in silico model with available software tools. Besides, the students account for the regulatory, standardisation, legal and ethical aspects by defining the corresponding requirements, if applicable, and discussing benefits and challenges of the chosen approach. In this respect, the students also reflect on how the credibility of the developed in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial could be assessed.

Learning goals

- Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medical devices;
- Critically reflect on a given case study of an in silico trial for medical devices in relation to the regulatory and ethical consideration;
- Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medical devices.
- Implement an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device with state-of-the-art software tools.
- Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device.
- Design a proper geometry for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device.
- Formulate recommendations on the how the credibility of the in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial should be assessed.

P09: Development of an in silico trial for a medical device - Part II

Description

The students continue on the development of the same in silico trial as in P08.

Learning goals

- Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medical devices;
- Critically reflect on a given case study of an in silico trial for medical devices in relation to the regulatory and ethical consideration;
- Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medical devices.
- Implement an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device with state-of-the-art software tools.
- Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device.
- Design a proper geometry for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medical device.

- *Formulate recommendations on the how the credibility of the in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial should be assessed.*

P10: Development of an in silico trial for a medicinal product - Part I

Description

The students develop an in silico trial for a given case study on a medicinal product with defined specifications. In the development process, the students situate the in silico trial in the development process of the medicinal product, determine the aim of the in silico trial, the available input and the desired output and create the in silico model with available software tools. Besides, the students account for the regulatory, standardisation, legal and ethical aspects by defining the corresponding requirements, if applicable, and discussing benefits and challenges of the chosen approach. In this respect, the students also reflect on how the credibility of the developed in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial could be assessed.

Learning goals

- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medicinal products;*
- *Critically reflect on a given case study of an in silico trial for medicinal products in relation to the regulatory and ethical consideration;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medicinal products;*
- *Implement an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product with state-of-the-art software tools;*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product;*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product;*
- *Formulate recommendations on the how the credibility of the in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial should be assessed.*

P11: Development of an in silico trial for a medicinal product - Part II

Description

The students continue on the development of the same in silico trial as in P10.

Learning goals

- *Outline a typical workflow for the development of in silico trials for medicinal products;*
- *Critically reflect on a given case study of an in silico trial for medicinal products in relation to the regulatory and ethical consideration;*
- *Showcase how in silico methods can contribute in different phases of the development process of medicinal products.*

- *Implement an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product with state-of-the-art software tools.*
- *Formulate proper boundary and loading conditions for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product.*
- *Design a proper geometry for an in silico model used in an in silico trial for a medicinal product.*
- *Formulate recommendations on the how the credibility of the in silico model and the corresponding in silico trial should be assessed.*

P12: Communication on in silico medicine

Description

Students present the developed in silico trials (for a medical device and a medicinal product) to an interdisciplinary audience. Students follow the presentation and summarize three presentations of fellow-students in max. 10 lines, by extracting the most essential aspects of each presentation.

Learning goals

- *Explain technical terms such as segmentation, registration, meshing and in silico modeling in layman's terms;*
- *Explain credibility terms such as verification, validation and uncertainty quantification in layman's terms;*
- *Identify how in silico models can contribute to a given clinical need.*